

Chalkones as Bactericidal Compounds

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Marrian *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1419) have prepared several aminochalkones on the basis that the grouping—C=C—CO—is present in many naturally occurring antibiotics, which may be responsible for the antibacterial activity. This type of grouping is also present in the chalkone. The bactericidal activity of chalkones has also been reported by Jeney *et al.* (*Zentr. Bact. parasitenk Abt. I Org.*, 1955, 163, 291 and Minorn *et al.* (*J. Agri. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1954, 28, 791) that *o*-furfurylideneacetone and dibenzylidenediacetone are markedly toxic to rats. Keeping this in view, several chalkones have been prepared by condensing 2-hydroxy-3,5-dichloroacetophenone with benzaldehyde, *p*-nitro-, *m*-hydroxy-, *p*-hydroxy-, *o*-chloro- and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehydes, *p*-tolualdehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, vanilline, α -naphthaldehyde, and β -naphthaldehyde, and *p*-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro- and 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-acetophenones with furfuryl aldehyde.

[X=alkyl group; R'=substituted groups]

The chalkones have been prepared by treating different acetophenone, (1.0*M*) with the appropriate benzaldehyde (2.2*M*) in 95% ethanol (25 c.c.) and 50% KOH (50 c.c.). This was thoroughly mixed by shaking and kept for 7 days. Subsequently dilute hydrochloric acid was added and the chalkones separating were crystallised from suitable solvents.

Bromination was carried out in acetic acid medium and the reactivity of the dibromide was examined with potassium iodide. All the dibromides gave the corresponding chalkones from which they were prepared as they did not show any depression in m.p. with the original chalkones (Vandervalla and Jadhav, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 746).

2,4-Dichlorophenyl acetate was prepared according to Chattaway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495).

2-Hydroxy-3,5-dichloroacetophenone.—The Fries rearrangement of the above ester was carried out according to Sen and Bhargava (this *Journal*, 1954, 26, 368).

Preparation of Chalkones.—To the appropriate acetophenone (1.0*M*), dissolved in 95% ethanol (25 c.c.), different aldehydes (2.2*M*) were gradually added to it, followed by a 50% solution of KOH (50 c.c.). The solution was well shaken and allowed to stand for 7 days at

the room temperature. The chalkone was obtained by neutralising with HCl (dil.) and re-crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

TABLE I

No.	Chalkone.	M.P.	Yield.	%Chlorine.		D i b r o m i d e.		%Total halogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	M.P.	Formula	Found.	Calc.
1.	2'-Hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro-	142°	82%	24.11	24.23	115-16°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂	50.00	50.00
2.	2'-Hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro- 4-nitro-	>265°	82	(N)4.09	4.14	160°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₄ NCl ₂ Br ₂	46.32	46.30
3.	2',3-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichloro-	165°	73	22.90	23.00	210°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	49.21	49.25
4.	2',4-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichloro-	200-201°	74	22.96	23.00	-	..	..	..
5.	2'-Hydroxy-2,3',5'-trichloro-	143°	65	32.48	32.52	143°	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₃ Br	54.60	54.60
6.	4-Dimethylamino-2'-hydroxy- 3',5'-dichloro-	194°	67	(N)4.14	4.16	110°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂ Br ₂	46.52	46.57
7.	4-Methyl-2'-hydroxy-3',5'- dichloro-	115°	69	23.10	23.15	160°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂	49.40	49.48
8.	4-Methoxy-2'-hydroxy- 3',5'-dichloro-	148°	68	21.90	21.99	85-90°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	47.78	47.82
9.	2'-Hydroxy-3',5'-dichloro- furfurylidene-	130°	75	25.01	25.09	102°	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	52.12	52.14
10.	2,2'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichloro-	159°	73	22.96	22.97	130°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	49.22	49.25
11.	2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,5'-dichloro- β -naphthylidene-	53°	87	19.62	19.78				
12.	1,2'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-dichloro- α -naphthylidene-	221°	76	19.62	19.78	95°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	44.50	44.50
13.	2',4-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy- 3',5'-dichloro-	137°	60	20.89	20.94	210°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ Cl ₂ Br ₂	46.23	46.29
14.	4'-Chlorofurfurylidene-	101°	79	15.24	15.27	145°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ Cl Br ₂	49.80	49.80
15.	2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro- furfurylidene-	b.p. 200/5mm	73	14.25	14.28	..	..	..	..
16.	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro- furfurylidene-	135°	80	14.24	14.28	123°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ Cl Br ₂	47.80	47.85

Dibromide was prepared by brominating the chalkone in acetic acid medium for one hour with a 10% solution of bromine in acetic acid.

Debromination was done by boiling with an equal weight of potassium iodide in presence of acetone for 4 hours and this led to regeneration of the chalkone.

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